

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	2010	B		Min: 63.1269 Max: 63.4003	1242 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1117-1124 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *roof tile collapse in "room 5"*

Covered by SU: 1232 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery R <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles F <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Coins f <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal f <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones m <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

SOIL/MATRIX: clay 25% silt 75% sand ___%
 Granular Layered Cohesive

Compaction	Color
<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) dark brown

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: Is bound to (only for masonry):

Is abutted by: Abuts: 1217

Is covered by: 1232 Covers: 1231, 1001 (bedrock)

Is cut by: Cuts:

Is filled by: Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: *- soil especially below tiles quite loose*
- excavated with trowels with occasional pick usage
- same soil fills round cut and curving cut into bedrock in NE area of Room 5.

Δ213 (terra cotta w/ fig. dec)
Δ214 (small worked bone)

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: *W end of excavated part of area B*

Shape: *irregular*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): *slopes to the S; rocks on E side; tiles throughout the rest*

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): *rocks on E side removed to reveal more tiles; tegulae and imbrices distributed evenly throughout; mostly oriented flat w bottom side down*

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): *uniform except for filling round cut and curving cut in bedrock beneath*

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

□ rubble wall
○ rock
** Δ213 (Terra cotta with figural decoration)*
◊ Δ214 (small worked bone)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

This layer, filled with broken roof tiles intermixed with painted plaster and soil probably represents either a collapse layer or a dump site for tile. Large amounts of broken tile (tegulae and imbrices) were found throughout the layer, varying in size from very small to just smaller than the size of a cassetta. A significant amount of rubble was also present, distributed throughout layer. Underlying the west end of the layer is a section of well-preserved crushed tufo floor; underlying the east end is bedrock. Underlying the center of the layer, where the tiles were most heavily concentrated, only a poorly preserved preparation layer for the tufo floor is present. This same layer fills the round cut and the curving cut in the bedrock in the NE area of the room (Room 5).

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

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Entered by on